

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN FOR QM4ST PROJECT (VERSION 1, 16.01.2023)¹⁹²

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document represents the 1st version of the QM4ST Data Management Plan (DMP). This document aims to describe the data management life cycle for the data sets that will be collected, processed or generated by the QM4ST project. QM4ST beneficiaries and partners will develop and periodically update this document (deliverable every 6 Months as described in the Sec. 7, M1.1 and in the Gantt Chart) outlining how the consortium will handle data, both during the project, and after the project has been completed. To update the DMP we will use the Data Stewardship Wizard. The data generated in the project are mainly linked to research activities and data will be published on an Open Access web platform accessible for verification and re-use. Not all data will be shared automatically, due to possible commercial sensitivity. Sharing can be requested and will be considered on a case-by-case basis, subject to confidentiality agreements. The DMP will be accessible via Zenodo repository under the CC BY 4.0 licence protection.

2. DATA SUMMARY

In the QM4ST project, the data defined as follows will be made accessible as defined by open research data policy (ORDP) e.g. the Sec. 7 of the feasibility study:

Type of the Data	The underlying data needed to validate the results in scientific publications including measured properties, spectra, charge density files, wave functions files, computer codes.
	Other data to be developed by the project: deliverable reports, meeting minutes, demonstrator videos, pictures from set-ups approved for dissemination by the consortium, technical manuals for future users, etc.
Format of the data	Electronic. The QM4ST consortium will assure that the format of the electronic data will be accessible according to the FAIR policy.
Size of the data	The size of the data is not expected to exceed the file size occurring in the course of the beneficiaries' research on a daily basis (100MB-1GB/per measurement or calculation). Only exception are spectroscopic data measured at synchrotron radiation sources (500GB/measurement).
Origin of the data	Majority of the underlying data will be a direct output from simulation software and/or equipment used. Other types of data will be written or prepared by the QM4ST researchers and support staff working on the project.
Utility of the data	To other researchers, allowing them to validate and disseminate the QM4ST project results, as well as exploit them in order to start their own investigations.

3. FAIR DATA

For the underlying data, the QM4ST consortium will use Zenodo repository (or alternatively Figshare, Dryad or the EU-funded B2DROP) for ORDP purposes since this repository facilitates linking publications and underlying data through persistent identifiers (DOIs) and data citations, as well as data archiving and linking datasets to Projects to increase their visibility. Moreover, most of the researchers involved in the QM4ST project already have a profile on Zenodo. Therefore, the FAIR data policy the QM4ST project follows is the one established by this repository. For the other data, the consortium will provide access using the project website (QM4ST.ntc.zcu.cz).

4. MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

DISCOVERABILITY: METADATA PROVISION

Metadata are created to describe the data and aid discovery. Beneficiaries will complete all mandatory metadata required by the repository and metadata recommended by the repository - Type of Data, DOI,

¹⁹²The structure of this document is based on the template <https://doi.org/10.48813/sstg-4g21>

Publication Date, Title, Authors, Description, Terms for Access Rights, and a link to a Zenodo Project as outlined in the repository instructions.

IDENTIFIABILITY OF DATA

Beneficiaries will maintain the Digital Object Identifier (DOI) when the publication/data has already been identified by a third party with this number. Otherwise Zenodo will provide each dataset with a DOI.

NAMING CONVENTION

A naming convention for uploading data to the repository is not mandatory, since the Zenodo repository includes a description of the dataset ensuring easy findability. However, for internal project purposes, the following guidelines are recommended:

Filename length: max. 40 characters; Characters: alphanumeric; including dot (.), underscore (_), and hyphen (-). Filename structure: clear and descriptive. Optionally, initials of the responsible person or a time note can be included. Examples: QM4ST_simulations_JM.txt; QM4ST_ARPES_Bi2Se3_2023_01.txt

APPROACH TOWARDS SEARCH KEYWORDS

Each author will make sure to include relevant keywords in the datafile description. All dataset generated by the project consortium will be also identified with the keyword QM4ST.

MAKING DATA OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

The underlying data related to scientific publications, the public deliverables and other datafiles included in Section 2 of this DMP will be made openly accessible via Zenodo and the project website.

The work-in-progress specifications of the QM4ST instrumentation, the data sheets and internal evaluations of the Research area's (RA) performance, laboratory records, working schemes and other data as agreed upon between the project consortium members are excluded from the ORDP and will not be made public in order to not jeopardise potential commercialisation and IPR protection of knowledge generated. The dissemination rules of all project results follow the provisions set in the QM4ST Consortium Agreement.

MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

Interoperability means allowing data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc. (i.e. adhering to standards for formats, as much as possible compliant with available (open) software applications, and in particular facilitating re-combinations with different datasets from different origins). QM4ST project ensures the interoperability of the data by using data in standard electronic formats (hdf5, png, raw, xml, ASCII), and using Zenodo repository with a standardised scheme for metadata.

INCREASE DATA RE-USE

Underlying data (with accompanying metadata) will be shared on Zenodo no later than publication of the related paper. Data will be accessible for re-use using the Creative Commons licenses provided by the Zenodo, without limitation during and after the end of the implementation period of QM4ST project. After the end of the project, data will remain in the repository, and any additional data related with the project but generated after its end will be also uploaded to the repository at the responsibility of the authors.

OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS

The academic codes that will generate the data are already, and will be in the future, released under open source-approved license to ensure suitable sharing and re-usability. All codes will be published in the GITHUB and own GITLAB server.

ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

QM4ST project will use Zenodo to make data openly available so there will be no infrastructure costs for the storage of the data. The personnel costs incurred in connection with the management of the data will be eligible as a part of the allocated resources within the grant.

DATA SECURITY

QM4ST will store the content across various secure services and repositories and also will make copies onto separate back up servers (e.g. *'Datová úložiště'* of cesnet.cz) to assure continuity and preservation in the event of service disruption.

ETHICS

No ethical issues apply to any data generated and processed by the QM4ST project.

CONCLUSIONS

This DMP is intended to be used by QM4ST project partners as a reference for data management (providing metadata, storing and archiving) within the project, on all occasions the data are produced. The project partners have contributed to and reviewed the DMP and are familiar with its use as part of WP1-5 activities. The Data Steward will also provide support to the project partners on using Zenodo and the project website as the data storage and management tool. The coordinating institution will ensure the research open data policy by verifying periodically the information uploaded to the repositories.